

**CHETLANUVCHI ARGUMENTGA EGA IKKINCHI TARTIBLI
CHIZIQLI DIFFERENSIAL TENGLAMALARNING DAVRIY
YECHIMLARI**

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АННОТАЦИЯ: Моделирование инженерных и экономических, биологических и медицинских и других прикладных задач приводит к необходимости исследования задач для обыкновенных дифференциальных уравнений с отклоняющимся аргументом. Исследованию одного из таких уравнений посвящена и настоящая работа. В работе рассматривается задача нахождения периодического решения для линейного дифференциального уравнения второго порядка с отклоняющимся аргументом.

КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА: дифференциальное уравнение с отклоняющимся аргументом, периодическое решение.

ABSTRACT: Modeling of engineering and economic, biological and medical and other applied problems leads to the need to study problems for ordinary differential equations with a deviating argument. The present work is also devoted to the study of one of these equations. The paper considers the problem of finding a periodic solution for a second-order linear differential equation with a deviating argument.

KEY WORDS: differential equation with deviating argument, periodic solution.

Chetlanuvchi argumentga ega ikkinchi tartibli chiziqli differensial tenglamalar fanning ko'plab masalalarini matematik modellashtirish vaqtida paydo bo'lib, bunday tenglamalar qatoriga chetlanuvchi argumentli o'zgarmas koeffitsientli chiziqli differensial tenglamalar ham kiradi [1-3].

Bu maqolada chetlanuvchi argumentli ikkinchi tartibli chiziqli bir jinsli bo'lmagan differensial tenglamalar qarashdiriladi, bunda qaralayotgan tenglamaning davriy yechimlarini topish masalasi bayon qilinadi.

Mayli ikkinchi tartibli o'zgaras koeffitsientli chiziqli bir jinsli bo'lmagan

$$x''(t) + px'(t - \tau) + qx(t) = f(t) \quad (1)$$

chetlanuvchi argumentli differensial tenglamaning davriy yechimlarini topish masalasini qaraylik, bu yerda p, q, τ o'zgaras sonlar. Bizga ma'lum, agar τ musbat son bo'lsa, u holda (1) tenglama etakchi argument, agar musbat son bo'lsa, unda tenglama kechiguvchi argumentli differensial tenglama bo'lib hisoblanadi. $f(t)$ funksiya bo'lsa

$$f(t) = \sum_{j=1}^n (A_j \cos \alpha_j t + B_j \sin \alpha_j t)$$

ko'rinishidagi funksiya, bu yerda $A_j, B_j, j = 1, 2, \dots, n$ berilgan o'zgaras sonlar.

Ko'rilayotgan masala, davriy yechimlarni topishdan iborat bo'lganligi sababli,

(1) ga bir jinsli

$$x''(t) + px'(t - \tau) + qx(t) = 0 \quad (2)$$

tenglamaning yechimi $x(t) = e^{\beta it}$ ko'rinishida topiladi. Bu holda β ga nisbatan

(2) bir jinsli tenglamaning xarakteristik tenglamasi deb ataladigan

$$\beta^2 - \beta i p e^{-\beta i \tau} - q = 0 \quad (3)$$

tenglamasiga ega bo'lamiz. Berilgan p, q va τ o'zgaras sonlari uchun k ning bazi bir butun $k = k_i, i = 1, 2, \dots, m$ qiymatlarida

$$\left((-1)^k p \pm \sqrt{p^2 + 4q} \right) \frac{\tau}{\pi} = 2k + 1 \quad (4)$$

tengligi o'rinli bo'lsin. Unda $\beta_i = \frac{\pi(2k_i + 1)}{2\tau}$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$ bo'lib, (2) tenglama

$$x(t) = \sum_{i=1}^m (C_{1i} \cos \beta_i t + C_{2i} \sin \beta_i t) \quad (5)$$

ko'rinishidagi davriy yechimga ega bo'ladi, bu yerda $C_{1i}, C_{2i}, i=1,2,\dots,m$ lar erikli o'zgarmas sonlar.

Haqiqatda ham (5) ni (2) ga qo'ysak

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{i=1}^m C_{1i} \left(-\beta_i^2 \cos \beta_i t - p \beta_i \sin \beta_i (t - \tau) + q \cos \beta_i t \right) + \\ & + \sum_{i=1}^m C_{2i} \left(-\beta_i^2 \sin \beta_i t - p \beta_i \cos \beta_i (t - \tau) + q \sin \beta_i t \right) = \\ & = - \sum_{i=1}^m C_{1i} \left(\beta_i^2 - p(-1)^{k_i} \beta_i + q \right) \cos \beta_i t - \sum_{i=1}^m C_{2i} \left(\beta_i^2 - p(-1)^{k_i} \beta_i + q \right) \sin \beta_i t = \\ & = - \sum_{i=1}^m \left(\beta_i^2 - p(-1)^{k_i} \beta_i + q \right) \left(C_{1i} \cos \beta_i t + C_{2i} \sin \beta_i t \right) = 0 \end{aligned}$$

bo'lib, bundan (5) ko'rinishidagi yechimning bir jinisli (2) tenglamani qanoatlandiruvchi ekanligi kelib chiqadi, bu yerda

$$\sin \beta_i (t - \tau) = -(-1)^{k_i} \cos \beta_i t, \quad \cos \beta_i (t - \tau) = (-1)^{k_i} \sin \beta_i t$$

va (4) shart bo'yicha o'rinli bo'ladigan

$$\beta_i^2 - p(-1)^{k_i} \beta_i + q = 0$$

tenglilari foydalanildi.

Bundan, (5) ko'rinishida aniqlanadigan $x(t)$ funksiyasi bir jinisli (2) tenglamani qanoatlandiradi.

Bir jinisli bo'lmagan (1) tenglamaning yechimi $\alpha_i \neq \beta_j$ uchun

$$x_0(t) = \sum_{j=1}^n \left(\tilde{A}_j \cos \alpha_j t + \tilde{B}_j \sin \alpha_j t \right) \quad (6)$$

ko'rinishida topiladi, bu yerda $\tilde{A}_j, \tilde{B}_j, j=1,2,\dots,n$ lar topilishi kerak bo'lgan o'zgarmas sonlar.

(6) ni (1) ga qo'yib va $f(t)$ ning ko'rsatilgan yechimini foydalansak

$$\sum_{j=1}^n \left[-\tilde{A}_j \alpha_j^2 \cos \alpha_j t - \tilde{B}_j \alpha_j^2 \sin \alpha_j t + p \alpha_j \left(-\tilde{A}_j \sin \alpha_j (t - \tau) + \tilde{B}_j \cos \alpha_j (t - \tau) \right) + \right.$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& +q(\tilde{A}_j \cos \alpha_j t + \tilde{B}_j \sin \alpha_j t) \Big] = \sum_{j=1}^m \left[-\tilde{A}_j \alpha_j^2 \cos \alpha_j t - \tilde{B}_j \alpha_j^2 \sin \alpha_j t - \right. \\
& -p\tilde{A}_j \alpha_j (\sin \alpha_j t \cos \alpha_j \tau - \cos \alpha_j t \sin \alpha_j \tau) + p\tilde{B}_j \alpha_j (\cos \alpha_j t \cos \alpha_j \tau + \\
& \quad \left. + \sin \alpha_j t \sin \alpha_j \tau) + q(\tilde{A}_j \cos \alpha_j t + \tilde{B}_j \sin \alpha_j t) \Big] = \\
& = \sum_{j=1}^m \left[(-\tilde{A}_j \alpha_j^2 + p\tilde{A}_j \alpha_j \sin \alpha_j \tau + p\tilde{B}_j \alpha_j \cos \alpha_j \tau + q\tilde{A}_j) \cos \alpha_j t + \right. \\
& \quad \left. + (-\tilde{B}_j \alpha_j^2 - p\tilde{A}_j \alpha_j \cos \alpha_j \tau + p\tilde{B}_j \alpha_j \sin \alpha_j \tau + q\tilde{B}_j) \sin \alpha_j t \right] = \\
& \quad = \sum_{j=1}^n (A_j \cos \alpha_j t + B_j \sin \alpha_j t).
\end{aligned}$$

Bundan $\cos \alpha_j t$ va $\sin \alpha_j t$ oldidagi koeffitsientlarni solishtirib, natijada noma'lum $\tilde{A}_j, \tilde{B}_j, j=1,2,\dots,n$ koeffitsientlarga nisbatan

$$\begin{cases} -\tilde{A}_j \alpha_j^2 + p\tilde{A}_j \alpha_j \sin \alpha_j \tau + p\tilde{B}_j \alpha_j \cos \alpha_j \tau + q\tilde{A}_j = A_j, \\ -\tilde{B}_j \alpha_j^2 - p\tilde{A}_j \alpha_j \cos \alpha_j \tau + p\tilde{B}_j \alpha_j \sin \alpha_j \tau + q\tilde{B}_j = B_j \end{cases}$$

algebrik tenglamalar sistemasiga ega bo'lamiz.

$$(q - \alpha_j^2 + p\alpha_j \sin \alpha_j \tau)^2 + (p\alpha_j \cos \alpha_j \tau)^2 \neq 0$$

bo'lgandan oxirgi sistema $\tilde{A}_j, \tilde{B}_j, j=1,2,\dots,n$ noma'lumlarga nisbatan yechimga ega bo'lamiz. Bundan noma'lum $\tilde{A}_j, \tilde{B}_j, j=1,2,\dots,n$ larni aniqlab, (6) ko'rinishidagi yechimga ega bo'lamiz.

Masalan: $p=1, q=-2, \tau=\frac{\pi}{4}$ va $3\cos t + 2\sin 3t$ uchun

$$x''(t) + x'\left(t - \frac{\pi}{4}\right) + 2x(t) = 3\cos t + 2\sin 3t \quad (7)$$

Tenglamasini ko'raylik. Bu holatda (4) tenglik

$$\left((-1)^k \pm \sqrt{1+4 \cdot 2}\right) \frac{1}{4} = 2k+1$$

ko'rinishga ega bo'lib, bu tenglik, k ning $k_1=-1$ va $k_2=0$ butun

qiymatlarida o'rinli bo'ladi. Bu holatda $\beta_{1,2} = \pm 2$ bo'lib, izlanayotgan tenglamaga bir jinisli bo'lgan tenglama $x(t) = A \cos 2t + B \sin 2t$ ko'rinishidagi yechimga ega bo'ladi, bu yerda A va B lar erikli o'zgarmaslar.

Endi bir jinisli bo'lmagan (7) tenglamaning yechimin

$$x_0(t) = A_1 \cos t + B_1 \sin t + A_2 \cos 3t + B_2 \sin 3t$$

ko'rinishida izlab, noma'lum koeffitsientlarni aniqlash uchun yechimning bu ko'rinishin berilgan tenglamadagi o'rinlariga qo'yamiz va noma'lum koeffitsientlarga nisbatan

$$\begin{cases} (2 + \sqrt{2})A_1 + \sqrt{2}B_1 = 6, \\ -\sqrt{2}A_1 + (2 + \sqrt{2})B_1 = 0, \\ (3\sqrt{2} + 14)A_2 + 3\sqrt{2}B_2 = 0, \\ 3\sqrt{2}A_2 + (3\sqrt{2} - 14)B_2 = 4 \end{cases}$$

algebrik tenglamalar sistemasiga ega bo'lamiz. Bu sistemadan noma'lum koeffitsientlarning $A_1 = \frac{3}{2}$, $B_1 = \frac{3(\sqrt{2}-1)}{2}$, $A_2 = \frac{3\sqrt{2}}{49}$ va $B_2 = -\frac{3\sqrt{2}+14}{49}$ son qiymatlarini aniqlab, natijada (7) tenglamaning

$$x_0(t) = \frac{3}{2} \cos t + \frac{3(\sqrt{2}-1)}{2} \sin t + \frac{3\sqrt{2}}{49} \cos 3t - \frac{3\sqrt{2}+14}{49} \sin 3t$$

ko'rinishidagi bir xususiy yechimga ega bo'lamiz.

Bundan, natijada berilgan (7) tenglamaga bir jinisli bo'lgan tenglamaning $x(t) = A \cos 2t + B \sin 2t$ umumiy yechimini hisobga olib, bu tenglamaning 2π davri bo'lgan umumiy yechimin

$$\begin{aligned} x(t) = A \cos 2t + B \sin 2t + \frac{3}{2} \cos t + \frac{3(\sqrt{2}-1)}{2} \sin t + \\ + \frac{3\sqrt{2}}{49} \cos 3t - \frac{3\sqrt{2}+14}{49} \sin 3t \end{aligned}$$

ko'rinishida yozishga bo'ladi.

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